

SCOUTING BY THE NUMBERS: PLATFORM METRICS, A&R STRATEGIES, AND NEW EXCLUSIONS IN TALENT DISCOVERY

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Abstract: This paper examines how the role of A&R professionals has evolved under the influence of platformisation, revealing significant shifts in talent discovery methods. Traditionally reliant on live performances, personal networks, and demo submissions, A&Rs now primarily scout talent through digital platforms (Spotify, TikTok, etc.), leveraging engagement metrics, online exposure, and algorithmic insights. The research delineates three core approaches: the ‘platform strategy’, the ‘preventive overexposure strategy’, and the ‘familistic strategy’. Although some of these methods may seem to adhere to traditional practices, this study discusses how digital transformation is reshaping established industry operations. Through qualitative analysis of semi-structured interviews with 25 A&Rs and industry insiders from both major and independent labels, the study discusses a paradigm shift towards systematic retrospective selection. The findings reveal that despite their distinct subcultural positioning, independent enterprises largely conform to similar selection patterns as their mainstream counterparts. This alignment raises significant concerns about the industry’s systematic disadvantaging of artists lacking digital proficiency, self-management capabilities, or self-branding skills. Indeed, even within purportedly alternative music sectors, the increasing prevalence of this selection model risks creating barriers for musicians who may struggle with platform visibility and digital marketing despite their artistic merit. These dynamics suggest a broader transformation of talent discovery practices, potentially limiting access to recording opportunities based on artists’ capacity to deal with digital environments rather than other aspects of their musical activity. Overall, the present study aims to contribute to ongoing scholarly debates on digital intermediation and cultural gatekeeping, offering insights into the evolving role of A&Rs as cultural intermediaries in a context dominated by algorithmic curation and user-generated content, ultimately advocating for a more inclusive approach to talent discovery beyond platform metrics.

Keywords: A&R practices, platform metrics, talent scouting, cultural commensuration, independent music industries, algorithmic visibility

The rumour of a voice

The music talent scout once belonged to a recognisable anthropology: a connoisseur with sturdy shoes and a good ear, haunted by the rumour of a voice. Today that rumour appears as a signal on dashboards, playlists, and analytics feeds. A&R work is a classic site of cultural intermediation. It links production to valuation, transforms aesthetic judgements into organisational decisions, and distributes opportunities across a field structured by unequal resources and forms of capital. In the present configuration, the evidentiary basis of judgment is increasingly imagined to reside in platform-derived traces. Playlists, virality, and engagement figures circulate as reference points that orient perception and coordinate action across labels, managers, promoters, and curators. What appears in numbers and dashboards is taken as evidence of promise, giving contour to what can be noticed and to whom attention can legitimately turn.

Research on platformisation describes an industry that increasingly reads circulation through data. For many practitioners, discovery begins where visibility has already taken shape, and the act of scouting becomes one of confirmation rather than revelation. The expectation that artists appear as measurable entities before entering organisational pipelines has become part of the common sense of selection, shaping how risk and promise are imagined in everyday practice.

The broader literature on A&R provides important context for these transformations. Historically, A&R departments served as essential intermediaries, controlling access to recording infrastructure and shaping the musical landscape (Frith, 1996; Negus, 1999; Rocchi, 2020). Research has documented how A&Rs accumulated and deployed cultural capital in balancing artistic evaluation with market considerations (Zwaan & ter Bogt, 2009), balanced tensions between art and commerce (Stratton, 1981), and drew on insider networks in filtering talent (Jones, 1998). Read through the lens theories of cultural intermediation (Bourdieu, 1984; Smith Maguire & Matthews, 2012; Ali et al., 2021), A&R work appears as a practice of value qualification, linking artistic potential to organisational recognition. Recent studies emphasise the impact of platformisation, where digital traces and streaming data increasingly structure A&R decision-making (Anderton et al., 2022), with independent and major labels alike converging around models that privilege visibility and marketability (Pilati et al., 2024; Webster et al., 2016; Marshall, 2019). Yet the effects of these shifts on scouting itself remain underexplored, particularly in specialised independent contexts where commitments to autonomy and authenticity encounter data-driven imperatives.

This article elaborates on findings I have presented in other studies (Raffa, 2025; Raffa, forthcoming). The empirical base consists of two rounds of semi-structured interviews with professionals in mainstream circuits and independent labels oriented to alternative genres, conducted between late 2022 and mid-2024, recorded, transcribed, and iteratively coded within an abductive frame; participants and organisations are anonymised. The sample is concentrated in the Global North and in specific genre niches, which sets the study's analytical horizon and the limits of generalisation.

Three strategies

Interviews with A&R managers and independent label representatives converge on three recurrent strategies that organise talent discovery in the current platform environment. Each strategy mobilises distinct evidentiary supports while aligning with an overarching logic of *ex-post* selection grounded in prior visibility.

1) *The 'platform strategy'*. Scouting concentrates on platform traces. Teams routinely track growth in streams, follower trajectories, editorial playlisting, and short-form video engagement, often through proprietary dashboards and weekly checks of Spotify's editorial lists such as *Fresh Finds*. Curators retain a filtering role within these data-centric routines, and label-editor relations are maintained as part of everyday practice. A&Rs described a distributed 'proxy' in which marketing units, data teams, and A&R staff circulate alerts that coalesce around unsigned artists showing organic lift across services; selection proceeds when multiple signals align. Interviewees also noted that, although automated scouting tools have proliferated, day-to-day work privileges in-house systems and analyst briefs over public third-party products. Industry investments exist, yet practitioners reported limited reliance on tools such as Musiio or Instrumental compared with internal pipelines. TikTok occupies a privileged position in early attention formation, where musical assessment intertwines with visual performativity, parasocial engagement, and an imagined sense of 'algorithmic compatibility' (Raffa and Pronzato, 2025) that A&Rs evaluate as part of cross-platform transferability.

2) *The preventive overexposure strategy*. A second configuration pre-tests market viability through legacy media spectacles. Television competitions and national showcases such as *The Voice* or *The X Factor* serve as public audition arenas that generate audience feedback at scale and shift early development costs to broadcasters. Labels then assess resonance and, where appropriate, secure potential returns through restrictive contractual arrangements. The practice is particularly salient for mainstream pop repertoires that struggle to achieve strong organic traction on platforms. It resonates with Negus's (1992) account of a 'synthetic ideology of creativity', now articulated through television's capacity to compress exposure and accelerate repertoire circulation (Graham, 2017). Interviewees described direct channelling of candidates into programmes and the use of these formats to keep a balanced repertoire in view for the mass market. Preventive overexposure thus functions simultaneously as risk displacement, repertoire management, and organised audience testing, while signalling that labels can still mobilise traditional media infrastructures alongside platform metrics. It should be noted, however, that this remains a residual strategy, involving a relatively small number of debuting artists and confined to mainstream acts or to independents willing to align with national-popular conventions.

3) *The 'familistic strategy'*. A third configuration foregrounds relational infrastructures. Access often depends on endorsements circulating within stable networks of managers, producers, artists, managers, studio owners, or other insiders, as well as through second-level partners such as independent labels that act as territorial or subcultural sensors under licensing or distribution agreements. These arrangements extend majors' reach into niches while allowing partners to retain parts of rights or control, making the

network itself a filtering device for attention and investment. The geography of work concerns positional access within the field. Proximity is symbolic, expressed through networks of managers, producers, and intermediaries who occupy central positions where opportunities circulate more densely. This concentration of relational capital reinforces symbolic boundaries that define who can legitimately enter consideration. The persistence of phrases such as “we do not accept unsolicited material” reflects this logic of exclusion, marking the limits of entry for those positioned at the margins of professional recognition. Although this strategy is typically pre-platform, interviewees suggested that its function has subtly shifted: faced with the perception that algorithmic visibility has diminished their discretionary power, insiders would seek to reaffirm their authority by relying even more strongly on trusted circuits, maintaining control through personal recommendation and networked validation.

Despite divergent media pathways, the three strategies share a structural principle. Each requires prior evidence of visibility as a threshold of legibility. Numbers from platforms, concentrated exposure through broadcast media, and endorsements from trusted intermediaries all function as preconditions for consideration. The result is a reorientation of scouting toward the confirmation of already circulating value claims and a displacement of risk toward artists who must first produce legible traces of demand before entering organisational pipelines for development.

Convergences

Independent labels have long narrated their difference as a cultural position anchored in scenes, aesthetic distinction, DIY repertoires, and slower artist development cycles. ‘Independence’ names a bundle of organisational forms and symbolic claims that mediate between autonomy and markets and that have historically secured legitimacy through proximity to niche communities and specialised knowledge (Hesmondhalgh & Meier, 2015; Oakes, 2009; Hibbett, 2005; Fonarow, 2006; Dale, 2009; Spencer, 2008; Bennett, 2018). As platformisation reorder circulation, these institutions continue to mediate between autonomy and market pressures while adapting their repertoires to digital visibility requirements. The interviews, though, show a different alignment. Indeed, across repertoires, acquisition increasingly proceeds on the basis of evidence already circulating online. The first gesture of recognition often arises from the perception of motion, as streams increase, followers accumulate, and traces of presence multiply across Spotify, TikTok, or YouTube. Independent labels watch for comparable signs within their own milieus, attending to Bandcamp activity or online exchanges, but the threshold of interest appears once visibility begins to feel tangible. The vocabulary shifts with context, the mechanism remains ex-post selection.

Respondents describe practical limits that drive this alignment. Scarce time and staff make unsolicited discovery uneconomical, while platform traces coordinate attention inside organisations. Even those who claim not to “chase Spotify numbers” use digital indicators as preliminary filters and only then apply scene knowledge for finer evaluation. The funnel starts with numbers and narrows through cultural judgement among those who pass the first screen. From these routines emerges the ‘credibility paradox’. Subcultural legitimacy erodes when an artist becomes very visible on

commercial platforms, while lack of visibility excludes them from consideration. Independent labels articulate the double bind clearly: being too offline makes an act un-signable, being too online risks undermining underground credentials. Convergence therefore operates as a threshold logic and a temporal expectation. Artists are asked to arrive 'platform-ready', able to sustain multi-channel engagement; labels then judge whether that engagement can be converted into durable publics without exhausting the identity of the project.

A further dimension of convergence lies in how participants experience the shaping power of formats. A&Rs and artists alike develop an intuitive sense of what sounds, lengths, and moods are likely to "move" across platforms. This perception becomes part of their everyday aesthetic reasoning, guiding choices before any explicit calculation takes place. Tracks that seem too slow, too long, or too structurally opaque are often sensed as unlikely to travel, even when valued on artistic grounds. In this way, the felt horizon of what can circulate begins to align across majors and independents. Experimentation persists, yet it moves within perceptual boundaries shaped by what practitioners imagine can circulate through platform space.

Taken together, these dynamics seem to dissolve the boundary between 'independent' and 'mainstream' as operational categories. Independence continues as discourse, catalogue policy, and community work, while admission criteria into pipelines become shared: prior validation, demonstrable self-management, and sustained audience engagement across interfaces.

Metrics

In the outlined context, platform metrics function as instruments of cultural "commensuration" (Espeland & Stevens, 1998), as they convert heterogeneous practices of listening, sharing, and viewing into comparable units that circulate as 'engagement', 'monthly listeners', and related indicators. In this conversion, traces of activity become inscriptions of value that can be ranked, exchanged, and mobilised inside organisations, making otherwise incomparable phenomena actionable within a single evaluative frame. These measures do not remain confined to organisational dashboards, as quantification of popularity has become an inescapable feature of cultural consumption itself, shaping not only how music circulates but how it is experienced aesthetically (Hanrahan, 2018). Visibility through numbers provides reassurance of belonging: consuming what is already widely consumed generates a sense of inclusion in the cultural present, while low counts signal marginality. In this way, quantification feeds into the affective and social dimensions of listening, transforming metrics into part of the pleasure of participation. Metrics also work as interpretive cues that orient how participants assess not just the popularity of a song but the value of their own engagement with it (Baym, 2018). Numbers frame perception, guide attention toward some artefacts and away from others, and insinuate themselves into the reflexive experience of audiences and professionals alike, operating doubly: as tools of organisational commensuration and as cultural signposts that format listening itself.

For A&R staff, these numbers provide an apparently objective language through which to communicate choices within organisations. They allow scouts to justify attention, managers to pitch signings to superiors, and departments to coordinate decisions across dispersed sites. In this sense, metrics do not merely assist evaluation: they structure what can be recognised as worthy of evaluation in the first place.

Interviews confirm this dual function. A&Rs often spoke of numbers as a ‘common language’ in which aesthetic impressions could be anchored and made legible for colleagues who did not share the same tacit knowledge of scenes. Dashboards, reports, and playlist statistics acted as intermediaries, creating a standardised form of visibility that travelled more easily within corporate hierarchies than the situated experience of a gig or a rehearsal. Recognition is a mediated achievement: artists must first generate quantifiable traces that can be mobilised as arguments within organisational deliberation.

Metrics also move across symbolic boundaries. Streaming counts or TikTok reach can serve as credentials for curators, promoters, and sponsors, opening opportunities that consolidate artistic careers. Numbers operate at once as internal instruments of commensuration and as external currencies of recognition. Data collected in dashboards are rearticulated as festival invitations, tour support, or brand partnerships, reinforcing the centrality of metric visibility in how artistic value is organised. Respondents also underlined the fragility of these numbers. Virality is volatile, algorithmic placement can vanish without warning, and the connection between online visibility and economic return often proves uncertain. Metrics retain authority because they organise attention and create evidence that moves easily inside organisations. What sustains their credibility is the coordination they permit among actors working within instability.

Exclusions

Scouting today assumes an artist who already performs core managerial functions: brand definition, steady content production, cross-platform scheduling, audience cultivation, and basic data literacy. This archetype aligns with the broader shift from DIY ethos to cultural entrepreneurship, where creative competencies are reframed as continuous enterprise (Bennett, 2018; Dale, 2009; Spencer, 2008; Khaire, 2017). Labels then treat visible ‘pre-positioning’ as proof of concept and concentrate attention on acts that have already organised themselves as marketable projects (Anderton et al., 2013). In interviews, this took practical form as expectations for regular posting cadences, digital media content competence, and responsiveness to playlist cycles, all read as signals that future work will integrate smoothly with platform infrastructures.

These demands create a filter that rewards artists who can convert time, money, and social support into self-management capacity. Musicians constrained day-to-day employment, limited production resources, weaker networks, caregiving responsibilities or discomfort with continuous self-exposure struggle to assemble the traces that labels recognise as investable. Ethical or stylistic refusals of TV formats or platform norms also carry a cost, since those circuits are now read as evidence pipelines. The result is a

patterned exclusion: creative skill, however defined, rarely suffices. Selection mechanisms tend to privilege those who combine musical competence with communicative labour and elementary analytical skills. The mixed gate intensifies this pattern. Metrics travel more effectively when managers, producers, or affiliated indie labels can translate numbers into organisational attention; without those ties, equivalent performance often stalls. In a multi-sided market where editorial curation and A&R interest loop into one another, the winners are typically artists who already act as small enterprises capable of sustaining visibility across interfaces. Those who cannot (or choose not to) perform that role face fewer points of entry and thinner prospects for development.

The ‘digital-physical feedback loop’

Numbers on screens become a working fiction that industry actors inhabit. Bookers, curators, managers, and artists read play counts and follower graphs as signs of a public that can be summoned. The figures circulate as a kind of currency: something to present in emails, to mention in calls, to place in one’s deck. What travels across platforms is then *restaged* in rooms, where the imagined audience behind the numbers is expected to appear. Interviewees described a practical sequence. Traces such as *recent playlist adds, steady month-over-month growth, clips that drew sustained attention* are bundled into a narrative of traction and offered to promoters as evidence of draw. Promoters, in turn, are believed to treat playlists as a proxy for local interest, even when the geography is uncertain.

In the independent music economy, the loop between digital visibility and physical practice is vividly concrete. Artists and small labels still depend on selling records and merchandise at live shows, but to reach those spaces, they believe they must first demonstrate quantifiable demand. Numbers are interpreted by professionals as signs that a viable audience exists, prompting the booking of shows that might otherwise never occur.

This economy of anticipation is built on belief. The numbers suggest the existence of a public that can be reached, a presence waiting somewhere beyond the screen. Each live event becomes a moment of verification: a way of testing whether the traces of attention that circulate online can take shape as bodies in space. Artists, managers, and promoters act within this expectation. They imagine the digital signals as a form of potential energy that performance might unlock. When people do appear, the event feels like the completion of a circuit, a brief coincidence between the imagined audience of the metrics and the living audience before them.

If you listen closely, really closely, you’ll hear it

Culture takes shape in bodies before it settles in numbers. Scenes cohere through proximity, shared time, and the minor rituals of rehearsal rooms, small venues, and improvised circuits of care. Platforms reorganise this terrain by installing a different horizon of expectation: value is anticipated through counts and curves, then sought

again in rooms that are booked on the strength of those same figures. What appears on a dashboard is treated as a promise of presence, and the live event becomes the test that might redeem the promise or expose its emptiness.

A profit-centred system trains participants to read those promises in similar ways. Artists learn to present themselves as manageable projects; labels and promoters come to treat visibility as a precondition for risk; curators develop habits of selection that privilege what already travels. Dissenting aesthetics, non-conventional musical forms, local languages, or practices anchored in embodied exchange find fewer points of entry. Parallel worlds proliferate: musicians who exist vividly inside online bubbles but leave no trace in the places where hybridisations and innovations typically begin.

Industry actors do not necessarily experience this as coercion from an opaque machine. They work with an imagined model of how visibility ‘works’, built from anecdotes, partial data, and institutional memory. That model simplifies uncertainty and nudges decisions toward the centre, where the numbers feel safer. Conformism follows from the desire to limit loss. Even so, inter-human relations continue to matter. Familistic endorsements, friendships, and local knowledge still move artists through the system, though these ties are increasingly channelled toward projects that look compatible with expected patterns of circulation.

The reality of these discussed transformations resides in how they are perceived and enacted. The field is animated by perceptions of how value is made and where it appears. Metrics organise those perceptions into common sense; embodiment gives them consequence. When bodies gather, the abstraction hardens into merch sold, guarantees honoured, calendars planned. When they do not, the abstraction collapses back into a trace on a screen. Between these outcomes sits a culture of anticipation that narrows available futures, privileges the recognisable, and filters out voices that might disturb the curve. Because once algorithms are in charge and branding is the cost of entry, what we end up with is not culture. It’s content. Loud. Clean. Predictable. So the machine keeps spinning. Metrics go up. A&Rs nod. Feeds refresh. And somewhere just outside the frame, someone is still playing. And if you listen closely, really closely, you’ll hear it. No followers. No rollout. No plan. Just music. You won’t hear it in the charts. Or in the ad. But if you stop scrolling, even for a second, you might. That thing the industry does not know how to count.

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